

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: JACKSON-FORBES****FIRST NAME: PHILIPPA****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Researching Topics and Writing an Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-9)
2. Adequate Usage of Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. American vs. British English Words: Spelling and Pronunciation (EUCLID 2021, 25-26)
4. Giving Credit to the Author and Source to Avoid Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-34)
5. Style Guide and its Importance (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ESSAY WRITING AT THE ACADEMIC LEVEL

1) INTRODUCTION

I reviewed and analysed Periods 1 and 2 of the course ACA-401D. The study material on essay writing was very insightful and delved into matters that were long forgotten. It was interesting and served as a refresher on how to write quality academic essays. EUCLID has provided detailed and critical information to guide its students when writing papers. If well understood and applied, the study material in Period 1 will serve as a foundation for all subsequent papers for submission. The different videos and documentation to be read, upon first glance, appear intimidating. Once I started to read however, clarity on essay writing began. I now feel even more motivated and ready to pursue the rest of the degree programme.

My response paper will discuss the research of topics to facilitate the writing of essays. It also looks at the usage of punctuation as well as the spelling and pronunciation of American words in comparison to those of the British. Plagiarism and the importance of giving credit to the author is also a component as well as style guides.

2) RESEARCHING TOPICS AND WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

Prior to writing an academic essay, it is necessary to understand how it differs from other types of essays. The academic essay does not include fictional nor mythical information. It should be based on research work and findings either published or unpublished (EUCLID 2021, 7). This ensures that the essay will be grounded on factual evidence which can then be used as the basis for a conclusion.

One should first assess what is already known and locate the findings which speak on that subject. Then, there needs to be research on what has not yet been identified and/or analysed. Both the known and unknown will provide the necessary support to communicate the writer's intention or point (Lester and Jr 2014). All sources must be credible or else the basis on which the argument was formed will not stand. Assessing what different sources state on the matter is necessary for a convincing argument. I should be prepared to review several angles to arrive at a sound conclusion. Creativity cannot be overstressed. "Creative thinking encourages you to broaden your ideas" (EUCLID 2021, 9). It will make for an interesting read and give clarity on the subject.

A key component to writing a good essay is ensuring adequate planning. Though there is no set way to communicate, planning ensures that the reader follows the arguments to arrive at the conclusion. The aim of the paper should be clear in the writer's mind and should consequently be analysed prior to commencing the essay (EUCLID 2021, 7). Another success factor is that of allotting sufficient time to formulate and structure the contents. This allows the writer to determine the findings that will provide strong foundation for the ideas being brought across.

3) ADEQUATE USAGE OF PUNCTUATION

Incorrect punctuation serves as a distraction to the reader as it may cause a shift from following the gradual build-up to the point. It is therefore pertinent that I am able to differentiate between correct and incorrect punctuation. One should aim to use as little punctuation as possible (EUCLID 2021, 16). Some of the important aspects of punctuation include apostrophes, brackets, bullet points and quotation marks. A brief synopsis of the usage of each type is outlined below.

a) Apostrophes

Apostrophes are used to demonstrate ownership and to indicate the omission of a letter. For the purpose of ownership, the students should note the difference between conjugating for single nouns and plural ones. It is not the same. The usage of apostrophes for the omission of letters is discouraged for academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 39).

b) Brackets

There are different types/shapes of brackets and are usually used to provide the reader with additional information (EUCLID 2021, 17). It is necessary to understand the usage of brackets with punctuation marks. It can either be before or after the closing bracket depending on the scenario. After reading this section, I saw how using brackets could be beneficial by providing additional information.

c) Bullet Points

When listing items, there is no requirement for punctuation at the end of each item. Punctuation should be placed at the end of sentences. This served to reinforce what I currently practice but it was good to also know that it was correct.

d) Quotation Marks

Quotation marks are used for direct speech and it is important for the student to understand the technique. After reading this section, it was determined that to minimise the risk of a higher plagiarism rate, it is best to note use direct speech unless it serves as a very strong foundation for a critical point being put forward.

Additionally, quotation marks can be used with other punctuation. Care should be taken when doing so. In most cases, it is best to keep sentences short and to the point (EUCLID 2021, 13). This reduces the chance of misunderstanding.

Though it may seem insignificant, errors with punctuation can be detrimental and may take away from the credibility of the writer. Punctuation also goes hand in hand with the language of the essay and this will be indicated in the next section.

4) AMERICAN VS. ENGLISH BRITISH WORDS: SPELLING AND PRONUNCIATION

Consistency is a key component of essay writing in general. It is equally or even more important in relation to academic writing. Consistency not only refers to the flow of the essay but also to the language displayed. Though both originate from English, there is a difference between American words and British Words (EUCLID 2021, 25). The style of punctuation is also somewhat different.

I was reminded that there are some words which are spelt the same but have different pronunciations. Likewise, there are words which sound the same but have different spelling. Other words may be spelt the same but have other or additional meanings. Writers are tasked with the responsibility of knowing the various meanings that

the words have. I should therefore format my sentences to facilitate understanding in the manner it was intended.

Punctuation is sometimes the same but at times, there is a variance (Algeo 2006, 12). A key way to ensure that the entire essay is done using the same language is to carefully analyse upon the completion of the first draft. Sometimes reviewing a paper a day or two after enables the writer to pick up on errors not previously seen. It also provides an opportunity to identify more suitable words to bring the point across. I will endeavour to practice this when writing my papers.

5) GIVING CREDIT TO THE AUTHOR AND SOURCE TO AVOID PLAGIARISM

Giving credit to the author shows an appreciation for the time and effort spent writing and compiling findings (Posner 2007). Plagiarism is not only unethical. It is also a punishable offence. This is the reason it is very critical that students ensure that all work is cited and the original work listed in the references to give credit.

Ensuring that the citation is indicated is one part of the process. The next part is to ensure that it is done correctly and there is uniformity with the type of citation used (Lester and Jr 2014).

I have been reminded by the Course Pack that citing is not necessary in every situation (EUCLID 2021, 37). One such scenario is when the information outlined is common knowledge and widely used. This can be ascertained if when checking various sources, the information is repeated on numerous occasions.

Otherwise, I will ensure to cite and to show my respect whilst writing each paper and at the end in the bibliography.

6) STYLE GUIDE AND ITS IMPORTANCE

Style Guides are used for technical writings such as academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 41). There needs to be order with all things academic. Therefore, though I am writing based on several works and findings retrieved, my end product should have a specific style format. This style is determined by the educational institution or the entity to which the essay will be given.

During my review of this subject, I discovered that authors have expressed discontent in conforming to specific styles of writing. This is based on the belief that it takes away from their creativity. My analysis however, shows that ideas can still be clearly displayed using ingenuity whilst conforming to the prescribed standard. It will therefore require a level of skill on my part. This also supports the reason writers' work should be

recognized and cited in the references section. On another note, conforming to a style may reduce the incidence of errors and save time used proofreading (EUCLID 2021, 42).

EUCLID recommends using Turabian (EUCLID 2021, 41) and I have therefore chosen to complete my doctorate programme using this method. It is my belief that this will minimize the possibility of disparity between course papers.

7) CONCLUSION

Writing an academic essay can be an exciting process. This is because it allows the reader to explore other writers' work and findings and compare them to explain a hypothesis. It is important for me to not get carried away when writing and only focus on the point being brought across. There are several things which must be adhered to and rules that should always be observed.

I am required to ensure that my writing is based on fact and on other pieces of research and/or findings whether published or unpublished. Considering the purpose and the point that I desire to bring across will determine the sources that I choose to include in my essay. Analysing findings for and against my point allows for clarity and direction. I need to plan and display my findings in a clear and logical fashion.

Punctuation plays a vital role in structuring the content. If not done correctly, it can detract from the message intended. It is also important to note that punctuation differs if using American words instead of British words. Language consistency throughout the essay reduces the risk of spelling and using words in American and British interchangeably.

A writer's time and effort compiling a paper should be acknowledged. I will therefore ensure that credit is duly given by citing all references and not trying to pass other writers' work as my own.

Though being assigned a style guide can be viewed as restrictive, it facilitates uniformity and order when writing. I will endeavour to use EUCLID's recommended style, Turabian in all future assignments including this one.

The information received in Periods 1 and 2 are beneficial and will certainly pave the way forward.

REFERENCES

Algeo, John. 2006. *British or American English?: A Handbook of Word and Grammar Patterns*. 1st edition. Cambridge; New York: Cambridge University Press.

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